

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES IN WEST BENGAL: POLICY VS REALITY FOR NEP 2020

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ABSTRACT

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes the importance of inclusive education for equitable learning opportunities for children with disabilities. This aligns with the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016, and global initiatives like Sustainable Development Goal 4. However, the implementation of this policy in West Bengal shows considerable shortcomings. This study assessed the current status of inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal, identified key challenges, and offered actionable recommendations. It involved a review of government reports, academic studies, and organizational research through a qualitative lens. The findings underscored significant obstacles, such as inadequate infrastructure—over 60% of schools lack ramps or accessible restrooms—and a shortage of trained educators, with only 18% having training in inclusive methods. Additionally, socio-cultural stigmas and low parental awareness further restrict educational access for children with disabilities, especially in rural regions. Systemic problems, including poor inter-departmental coordination and limited oversight, exacerbate these issues. The study recommended enhancing school infrastructure, requiring teacher training in inclusive education, promoting awareness campaigns, and utilizing technology to assist students with disabilities.

Keywords: Disability, Inclusive Education, NEP 2020, Policy Challenges

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education emphasises the integration of all learners, regardless of their abilities, into mainstream educational settings, fostering equality and respect. In addition, NIOS will develop high-quality modules for teaching Indian Sign Language and other essential subjects in Indian Sign Language (Kumar & Singh, 2022). Inclusive education is an approach to learning that emphasises diversity as its core principle (Aithal & Aithal, 2020). The National Education Policy

(NEP) 2020 envisions inclusive education as a cornerstone of India's educational reforms, aiming to ensure equitable access and opportunities for children with disabilities (Shah et al., 2016). By recognising diversity as an asset, the policy emphasises that all learners, including those with disabilities, should be educated alongside their peers (GoI, 2020). However, implementing such an ambitious vision presents challenges, particularly in states like West Bengal, where systemic issues and regional disparities persist (Das, 2021). West Bengal, known for its diverse socio-cultural fabric and historical commitment to education, presents a unique context for studying the implementation of NEP 2020's inclusive education policies. According to Census 2011, the state has over 2 million persons with disabilities, with a significant proportion in school-going age groups (Bhat & Geelani, 2017). Despite legislative frameworks like the Right to Education (RTE) Act, 2009, and the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPwD) Act, 2016, ensuring access to quality education for Children with Special Needs (CwSN) remains a complex issue. NEP 2020 seeks to address these barriers by proposing measures such as sensitising teachers, using assistive technologies, and integrating special educators into the system (GoI, 2020). Furthermore, it emphasises cross-sectoral collaboration among educational institutions, healthcare systems, and community organisations. However, the transition from policy to practice is fraught with hurdles (Shah et al., 2016). Research suggests that while policies may be well-intentioned, their implementation often encounters resistance due to gaps in resources, lack of awareness, and insufficient administrative support.

Franzkowiak (2009) emphasised that basic courses in inclusive education have become mandatory, and inclusive pedagogy, along with pedagogical practice, is increasingly being considered an essential component in basic teacher training programmes. Mukherjee and Das (2019) expressed those challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, inadequate teacher training, and social stigma hinder the achievement of the goal of inclusive education. The state of West Bengal has taken steps to operationalise inclusive education through initiatives such as the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) and Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC). Despite these efforts, ground realities revealed significant gaps in resource allocation, teacher preparedness, and infrastructural development. Studies highlighted that rural areas in the state, in particular, struggle with accessibility and awareness, leading to lower enrolment and retention rates among CwSN (Sarkar & Gupta, 2022). This gap between policy and reality necessitates a critical examination of the challenges and opportunities within the framework of NEP 2020. This study explored the dichotomy between policy aspirations and ground realities in implementing NEP 2020's inclusive education provisions for children with disabilities in West Bengal. It seeks to identify systemic challenges, evaluate the effectiveness of current interventions, and provide recommendations to bridge the gap. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the discourse on inclusive education, highlighting the need for localised, context-sensitive approaches to ensure no child is left behind.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Looking back in history, we find that the Church Missionary Society initiated formal education for the disabled in India in 1869. Even today, education for the disabled in India

largely relies on charities or non-governmental organisations (NGOs). There are very few government-run educational institutions for this group, leaving most disabled children in rural areas without access to schooling (Sharma & Loreman, 2021). Notably, most of the special schools run by NGOs are concentrated in urban areas.

While terms such as equality, equity and inclusion are frequently mentioned in policy statements, significant gaps remain from the perspective of disabled workers. One such concern is the proposal to group schools into a school complex (Kumar & Singh, 2022). As outlined in the NEP, this complex will include a secondary school along with other schools and anganwadis within a radius of 5-10 km (Das, 2021). However, it is not clear how special schools will be included in this framework (Kumar & Singh, 2022). What is the impact of the privatisation of educational institutions on the disabled community? The RPD Act only reserves seats in government-run higher education institutions, with private institutions having no obligation towards these students (Broderick & Lalvani, 2017). It is crucial to remember the strong link between disability and poverty. As a result, making education a costly commodity will disproportionately affect the disabled population and other marginalised groups (Aithal & Aithal, 2020).

What is the impact of the privatisation of educational institutions on the disabled community? The RPD Act only reserves seats in government-run higher education institutions, with private institutions having no obligation towards these students. It is crucial to remember the strong link between disability and poverty (Beacham & Rouse, 2012). As a result, making education a costly commodity will disproportionately affect the disabled population and other marginalised groups. If implemented, NEP 2020 will make education accessible to most children from middle and lower socio-economic backgrounds, as well as to people with disabilities, regardless of their potential or abilities (Kumar & Singh, 2022).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- O₁ : To evaluate the status of inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal based on research reviews regarding NEP 2020.
- O₂ : To identify key challenges that hinder inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal, as indicated by research reviews regarding NEP 2020.
- O₃ : To propose further suggestions through research reviews for achieving successful inclusive education for children with disabilities based on NEP 2020 guidelines.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS OF THE STUDY

- RQ₁ : What is the status of inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal based on research reviews regarding NEP 2020?
- RQ₂ : What are the key challenges that hinder inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal, as indicated by research reviews regarding NEP 2020 ?

RQ₃ : What further suggestions can be proposed through research reviews for achieving successful inclusive education for children with disabilities based on NEP 2020 guidelines ?

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This study utilised a bibliographic research design, based on a systematic analysis of existing scholarly and policy-related literature. Such bibliographic research is particularly effective for exploring educational policies and their real-world impacts, as it enables researchers to analyse patterns, trends, and gaps from documented sources rather than collecting primary data (Gil, 2008).

In this study, the sample comprised a carefully selected collection of documents, including:

- National policy texts (e.g. NEP 2020, RPwD Act 2016),
- Peer-reviewed journal articles,
- Government reports (e.g. RCI, UNESCO, UNICEF),
- NGO documentation and project evaluations.

Data collection involved purposive sampling of pertinent secondary sources through academic databases such as JSTOR, Google Scholar, and official Indian education policy repositories. These sources were chosen based on their relevance, reliability, and recent publication dates (2016–2024).

Data analysis was conducted using a thematic approach. The extracted content was coded into emerging themes, including infrastructure challenges, teacher preparedness, policy implementation gaps, and socio-cultural barriers. This thematic synthesis facilitated the triangulation of insights across various document types, allowing for a critical examination of the disparity between policy and practice in inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal (Bowen, 2009). This bibliographic analysis served both exploratory and evaluative purposes, aiming to connect legislative intent with the actual educational landscape. It laid the groundwork for developing evidence-based recommendations that align with NEP 2020's inclusive objectives. Government documents (NEP 2020; RPwD Act, 2016), academic studies, journal articles, and reports from NGOs and international organisations were scrutinised to identify themes about implementation gaps, barriers, and best practices in inclusive education.

FINDINGS

Findings on O₁ and RQ₁

NEP 2020 aims to integrate children with disabilities into the mainstream education system, ensuring equitable access to quality learning. In West Bengal, although some initiatives have been introduced to further this aim, the results of their implementation are mixed. To clarify this goal, the researchers identified Government Initiatives, Early Childhood Education (ECE), and Policy Alignment as key areas for evaluating inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal under NEP 2020. These elements highlight the researchers' view that

effective governmental policies, early educational programs, and alignment between national and state policies are essential for successful inclusion. Concentrating on these domains facilitates a thorough understanding of the systemic efforts and challenges faced in implementing inclusion education.

Government Initiatives

To support students with disabilities, West Bengal has implemented programmes such as the Inclusive Education for Disabled at Secondary Stage (IEDSS) (Joshi, 2023). These initiatives aim to provide resources, assistive devices, and special educators to facilitate inclusive education. However, their impact remains limited, especially in rural areas, where less than 30% of schools are equipped with basic accessibility features, such as ramps, accessible toilets, and assistive learning tools (RCI, 2021). This disparity highlighted the challenges of scaling inclusive education policies in diverse socio-economic settings.

Early Childhood Education (ECE)

NEP 2020 underscores the importance of foundational literacy and numeracy for promoting inclusive education, particularly at the early childhood level. Despite this emphasis, only 12% of Anganwadi centres in West Bengal are equipped to accommodate children with disabilities (UNICEF, 2022). The lack of trained staff, assistive learning materials, and inclusive teaching practices at this critical stage of education impedes the state's ability to lay a strong foundation for children with special needs.

Policy Alignment

West Bengal has taken steps to align its education policies with the mandates of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPwD) Act, 2016. While the incorporation of these mandates into the state's policy framework represents progress, the absence of clear operational guidelines often results in fragmented and inconsistent execution (Mukherjee & Dutta, 2022). This gap between policy design and implementation undermines efforts to create a cohesive and effective inclusive education system.

Findings on O₂ and RQ₂

The researchers categorized the results into four domains: Infrastructure Deficiencies, Teacher Training and Capacity Building, Socio-cultural Barriers, and Systemic and Policy Gaps. This framework was developed to systematically identify and address the various challenges that hinder inclusive education for children with disabilities in West Bengal, as noted in research related to NEP 2020. Each category identifies specific issues: physical and technological barriers obstruct the infrastructure; skill gaps and teacher retention problems impact educational delivery; societal stigma and insufficient parental awareness restrict social integration; and ineffective monitoring, along with poor inter-departmental coordination, demonstrate systemic shortcomings. This organized framework enables a thorough analysis, directing targeted interventions to promote inclusivity education.

Table 1: Challenges Hindering Inclusive Education for Children with Disabilities in West Bengal

Category	Challenges	Details	Sources
Infrastructure Deficiencies	Physical Barriers	Over 60% of schools in West Bengal lack ramps, elevators, or accessible toilets, impeding the enrolment and retention of students with physical disabilities.	Das & Biswas, 2021
	Technological Gaps	Limited internet connectivity (below 45% in rural areas) restricts access to platforms like DIKSHA that provide assistive content for inclusive education.	UNESCO, 2022
Teacher Training and Capacity Building	Skill Gaps	Only 18% of teachers in West Bengal have received training in inclusive pedagogy, and special educators are concentrated in urban areas, leaving rural schools underserved.	Sarkar & Ghosh, 2021
	Retention Challenges	Low salaries and limited professional development opportunities contribute to the high turnover of special educators, affecting the continuity of support for students.	RCI, 2021
Socio-cultural Barriers	Stigma and Discrimination	Cultural biases and stigmatisation in rural communities deter families from enrolling children with disabilities in mainstream schools.	Das, 2021
	Low Parental Awareness	Families in economically weaker sections often prioritise vocational training over formal education, limiting opportunities for children with disabilities.	Mukherjee & Dutta, 2022
Systemic and Policy Gaps	Weak Monitoring and Accountability	NEP 2020 lacks a robust monitoring framework; schools often do not undergo regular evaluations based on inclusivity criteria, leading to weak accountability.	UNESCO, 2022
	Inefficient Inter-departmental Coordination	Poor coordination between education and social justice departments causes delays in resource allocation and policy implementation, weakening efficiency.	Das & Biswas, 2021

Table 2: Recommendations for Achieving Successful Inclusion according to NEP 2020

Category	Recommendations
Infrastructure Enhancement	NEP 2020 Recommendation: The policy advocates universal physical accessibility in schools through features like ramps, barrier-free toilets, and signage to promote equitable participation of children with disabilities.
	Researchers' Suggestion: The researchers highlight that over 60% of schools in West Bengal, particularly in rural areas, still lack basic infrastructure for children with disabilities. They recommend that the state education department conduct annual accessibility audits and that government funding be prioritized toward inclusive infrastructure. Collaborations with NGOs and CSR-funded programs can accelerate this transformation, especially in backward districts.
Teacher Training and	NEP 2020 Recommendation: The policy underlines the necessity of embedding inclusive education within pre-service teacher education, in-service training, and hiring qualified special educators for every school complex.
Recruitment	Researchers' Suggestion: According to the researchers, only 18% of teachers in West Bengal are trained in inclusive pedagogy. They recommend embedding inclusive modules in D.El.Ed and B.Ed. Curricula through the SCERT and NCTE framework. Additionally, the deployment of special educators in every block—rather than just urban zones—is necessary. Salary increments and rural service incentives should be offered to reduce attrition among special educators.
Digital and Technological Inclusion	NEP 2020 Recommendation: To overcome learning barriers, NEP promotes the use of assistive technology and inclusive e-content on platforms like DIKSHA and NIOS, especially for learners with hearing, visual, or cognitive impairments.
	Researchers' Suggestion: The researchers observe a severe digital divide in rural West Bengal—less than 45% of students have regular internet access. They advocate for the distribution of regionally customized learning apps that integrate features like Indian Sign Language, audio narrations, and visual supports. Moreover, the government should subsidize smart devices for children with disabilities from low-income households.
Awareness and Advocacy	NEP 2020 Recommendation: NEP stresses the importance of sensitization programs and community involvement in reducing stigma and promoting acceptance of children with disabilities.
	Researchers' Suggestion: The researchers emphasize that socio-cultural stigma remains a deep-rooted issue, particularly in rural belts of Bengal. They propose community sensitization campaigns in collaboration with Panchayats, Anganwadis, and SHGs. Formation of active Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) focused on inclusive goals is also suggested to empower families and reduce school dropout rates among children with disabilities.

Category	Recommendations
<p style="text-align: center;">Policy Reforms</p>	<p>NEP 2020 Recommendation: NEP stresses the importance of sensitization programs and community involvement in reducing stigma and promoting acceptance of children with disabilities.</p>
	<p>Researchers’ Suggestion: The researchers emphasize that socio-cultural stigma remains a deep-rooted issue, particularly in rural belts of Bengal. They propose community sensitization campaigns in collaboration with Panchayats, Anganwadis, and SHGs. Formation of active Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) focused on inclusive goals is also suggested to empower families and reduce school dropout-rates among children with disabilities.</p>

This table provided a clear and organised overview of the recommendations for achieving successful inclusion. By addressing these critical areas, these suggestions aim to create a robust framework for inclusive education in West Bengal, ensuring that children with disabilities have access to equitable and quality education.

CONCLUSION

Assistive devices, technology-based tools and teaching-learning materials in appropriate languages will be made available to support this aspect of NEP 2020. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) recognises the need to establish supportive systems to meet the needs of children with disabilities (Tiwari & Kumar, 2021). The NEP 2020 outlines a transformative vision for inclusive education, emphasising the integration of children with disabilities into mainstream schooling (Kumar, 2020). However, its implementation in West Bengal revealed persistent systemic, infrastructural, and socio-cultural barriers. Challenges such as inadequate accessibility, insufficient teacher training, limited digital inclusion, and prevailing stigmas underscore the gap between policy aspirations and ground realities. To bridge this gap, a collaborative and multi-stakeholder approach is essential. Government agencies must take the lead in strengthening infrastructure and formulating actionable policies, while educators and teacher training institutions must prioritise skill development and inclusive pedagogy (Gonmei et al., 2023). Parents, communities, and NGOs have pivotal roles in advocacy, awareness, and fostering an environment of acceptance and support for children with disabilities (Panditrao, 2020). By investing strategically in accessibility, teacher preparedness, technological solutions, and community sensitisation programmes, West Bengal can move closer to achieving the goals of NEP 2020 (Kasinathan et al., 2023). Transforming the education system into one that genuinely values diversity and empowers children with disabilities is not only a legal mandate but also a moral imperative. This effort will ensure that every child, irrespective of their abilities, has the opportunity to learn, grow, and thrive in an inclusive society.

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